

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN KAZAKH AND ENGLISH LITERATURE IN THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract: The 20th century was a transformative period for literature across the world. Kazakh and English literature developed under vastly different historical, political, and cultural circumstances, shaping their unique trajectories. Kazakh literature was deeply influenced by the Soviet Union's policies, emphasizing socialist realism, collectivization, and the preservation of Kazakh identity through oral traditions. English literature, on the other hand, was marked by the modernist and postmodernist movements, exploring themes of existentialism, individuality, and social disintegration. This article provides an in-depth comparison of the two literary traditions, analyzing their historical contexts, dominant forms, thematic concerns, stylistic approaches, and societal representations.

Keywords. Kazakh literature, English literature, Soviet influence, modernism, postmodernism, national identity, collectivization, existentialism.

Introduction. The 20th century witnessed dramatic global changes, including two world wars, the rise and fall of empires, industrialization, and ideological shifts. These changes left a profound impact on literature, transforming it into a mirror reflecting the struggles, aspirations, and cultural values of different societies. Kazakh and English literature, though separated by geography and culture, share certain universal elements while exhibiting striking contrasts. Kazakh literature retained its strong ties to oral traditions, reflecting the struggles of Soviet rule and national identity. In contrast, English literature evolved through experimentation, marked by the modernist and postmodernist movements.

This article aims to explore the differences between these literary traditions by examining their historical backgrounds, literary forms, themes, and stylistic innovations.

1. Historical and Political Context

Kazakh Literature

The 20th century was a period of political and social upheaval for Kazakhstan. Under Soviet rule, Kazakh literature became a tool for political propaganda, adhering to the principles of socialist realism. Writers were expected to glorify communist ideals, promote collectivization, and suppress nationalistic sentiments. Intellectuals like Akhmet Baitursynov, Magzhan Zhumabayev, and others who resisted Soviet ideology faced persecution, imprisonment, or execution during Stalin's purges.

Despite these challenges, Kazakh writers and poets preserved elements of traditional oral literature, such as epics, legends, and lyrical poetry. This period also saw the rise of Russian-Kazakh bilingualism, with many works written in Russian to reach broader audiences while navigating Soviet censorship.

English Literature

English literature experienced a relatively freer creative environment, shaped by the global events of the century. The aftermath of World War I led to disillusionment and the emergence of modernism, which rejected traditional forms and focused on introspection and experimentation. Writers like James Joyce, Virginia Woolf, and T.S. Eliot explored the fragmentation of identity and society.

The end of colonialism and the rise of globalization also influenced English literature, with themes of identity, power, and cultural hybridity emerging in the works of postcolonial writers like Chinua Achebe and Salman Rushdie. [8]

2. Dominant Literary Forms

Kazakh Literature

Poetry remained the dominant literary form in Kazakh literature throughout the 20th century, deeply rooted in oral traditions. Poets like Mukagali Makatayev and Olzhas Suleimenov combined classical Kazakh poetic forms with contemporary issues, reflecting the struggles of the Kazakh people.

Prose also gained prominence, with novels and short stories addressing themes of rural life, collectivization, and cultural preservation. Writers like Gabit Musrepov and Mukhtar Auezov created works that depicted the lives of ordinary people against the backdrop of Soviet policies, such as Auezov's *Abai's Path*, which became a cornerstone of Kazakh prose. [1]

English Literature

English literature was dominated by novels, essays, and plays. Modernist authors like D.H. Lawrence and E.M. Forster explored the complexities of human relationships and societal change. Drama flourished with playwrights like Samuel Beckett and Harold Pinter, who redefined theatrical conventions with minimalist and absurdist elements. [2]

Poetry also underwent significant transformation, with figures like W.B. Yeats and T.S. Eliot embracing modernist techniques such as free verse, symbolism, and fragmentation. [3]

3. Themes and Motifs

Kazakh Literature

Kazakh literature focused on themes of national identity, tradition, and the challenges posed by Soviet collectivization and industrialization. Writers often used allegory and symbolism to critique Soviet policies while celebrating Kazakh cultural heritage.

The trauma of forced collectivization, famine, and political repression were prominent motifs in Kazakh prose and poetry. These themes were explored through depictions of rural life, community struggles, and the resilience of the Kazakh spirit.

English Literature

English literature, especially modernist works, dealt with themes of alienation, existentialism, and the fragmentation of identity. The disillusionment following World War I led to a questioning of traditional values and societal norms.

Postmodernism, which emerged in the mid-20th century, introduced themes of cultural relativism, parody, and the instability of meaning. Writers like Kurt Vonnegut and Thomas Pynchon used metafiction and satire to challenge conventional narratives.

4. Language and Style

Kazakh Literature

The language of Kazakh literature was shaped by its oral traditions, featuring lyrical expressions, proverbs, and vivid imagery. However, Soviet policies led to the Russification of Kazakh literature, with many works written in Russian. This bilingualism created a unique literary style that blended Kazakh cultural elements with Soviet ideology.

English Literature

English literature of the 20th century was marked by innovation and experimentation with language. Modernist writers like James Joyce used stream-of-consciousness techniques and complex syntax, while poets like Ezra Pound experimented with imagery and structure. Postmodernist writers often employed metafiction, intertextuality, and linguistic playfulness. [4]

5. Representation of Society

Kazakh Literature

Kazakh literature served as a reflection of collective struggles, emphasizing community values, cultural heritage, and resilience. Writers depicted rural life and the challenges of modernization, often critiquing Soviet policies indirectly through allegory and folklore.

English Literature

English literature, in contrast, often focused on individual experiences, exploring psychological depth and existential questions. Urbanization, industrialization, and globalization were recurring themes, reflecting the complexities of modern life.

Conclusion. Kazakh and English literature in the 20th century illustrate two distinct literary traditions shaped by unique historical and cultural contexts. Kazakh literature, deeply rooted in oral traditions, grappled with the challenges of Soviet oppression and cultural preservation. English literature, marked by greater creative freedom, embraced modernist and postmodernist experimentation, addressing universal human concerns. These literary traditions highlight the power of literature to reflect and shape the human experience across diverse cultural landscapes.

Referances:

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